

Experimental Evaluation of Dynamic Resource Orchestration in Multi-Layer (Packet over Flexi-Grid Optical) Networks

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Abstract Network services in 5G will be rolled out as pools of Virtual Network Functions (VNFs) exploiting the advantages of both Software Defined Networking (SDN) and Network Function Virtualization (NFV). In this context, 5G network services are envisaged as ordered sequences of VNFs resulting in the so-called VNF Forwarding Graphs (VNFFGs). Such VNFs can be allocated over a number of distributed but interconnected data centers (DCs). In this work, a Cloud/Network Orchestrator is discussed to dynamically process and accommodate VNFFG requests over a pool of DCs interconnected by a multi-layer (packet/flexi-grid optical) transport network infrastructure. Two different cloud and network resource allocation algorithms are proposed aiming at: *i*) minimizing the distance between the selected DCs; *ii*) minimizing the load (i.e., consumed cloud resources) of the chosen DCs. In the performance evaluation, the proposed algorithms are experimentally validated and compared on the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed.

Keywords Resource Orchestration · SDN · NFV

1 Introduction

5G networks are designed and being deployed to effectively take advantage of the benefits brought by both softwarized networks and virtualization tech-

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niques (e.g., SDN and NFV). Resulting 5G network services are made up of sets of interconnected network functions hosted in the cloud and running on top of commercial-off-the-shelf servers as virtual machines (i.e., VNFs). In this context, ETSI NFV defined an architectural framework for the coordinated VNF MANagement and Orchestration (NFV MANO framework [1]) also across different hypervisors and computing resources deployed in remote cloud infrastructures (i.e., DCs) [2]. The resulting logical VNF topology accommodating a network service is defined as VNF Forwarding Graph (VNFFG) [3]. It is required that the VNFs placed in distant DCs and their interconnections ensure QoS demands and Service Level Agreements (SLAs). SLAs can be defined via a number of key performance indicators depending on the nature of the network service itself. For instance, using the availability, the minimum bandwidth, the maximum end-to-end latency, the current load of both cloud and network resources [4]. Consequently, dealing with the network service SLAs entails to properly select the compute and network resources to be allocated at the DCs but also the interconnectivity among those DCs. For the latter, the DC interconnectivity is based on an heterogeneous (packet and flexi-grid optical) transport infrastructure (i.e., Multi-Layer Network - MLN).

A cloud and network resource orchestration system is proposed to compute and allocate the required resources to satisfy the incoming network services and their targeted SLAs. The implications when dynamically serving such VNFFG requests on top of the adopted MLN are thoroughly discussed. The cloud and network resources orchestration is performed by an allocation engine (herein referred to as *Allocator*). The *Allocator* complements the ETSI NFV Orchestrator (NFVO) when dynamically selecting the DCs and the required interconnections underpinning the requested VNFFGs over a distributed DC infrastructure interconnected by a MLN [5]. Every DC is physically attached to packet switch node (e.g., MPLS), named as packet Gateways (Gws). Gws are equipped with sliceable bandwidth variable transceivers (S-BVTs) providing the interconnection among them over a flexi-grid metro/core optical network. For each new VNFFG request, the *Allocator* computes the cloud and networking resources. If the computation succeeds then the *Allocator* communicates with dedicated controllers to program such resources. For the networking resources, the *Allocator* interacts with a Transport SDN Controller (T-SDN) [7]. The T-SDN controller allows the MLN resource computation and configuration. In this MLN, the adopted computation algorithms are proposed to achieve effective adaptation between the dual-layer technology (i.e., packet over optical) but also promoting *grooming* to attain the most efficient use of the network resources.

In the light of above considerations, we propose two on-line resource orchestration algorithms for selecting (virtual) resources. The term on-line is herein used to stress the fact that the algorithms are dynamically triggered to serve incoming VNFFG requests. That is, for each request the proposed algorithms aim at fulfilling the requests demands considering the current and updated view of the resources in both the DC and the transport MLN infrastructure. For the sake of completeness, virtual resources are (*i*) compute

resources at the cloud DCs hosting VNFs, and *(ii)* network links enabling the VNFs interconnection over the MLN infrastructure. Regardless of the adopted algorithm, the objective function is to deploy and satisfy the VNFFG requirements and also achieve the most efficient use of all the resources. This objective is usually tackled into the problem of embedding a virtual network onto a physical cloud/transport infrastructure, which is commonly referred to as Virtual Network Embedding (VNE) [8]. Herein, the VNE problem is decomposed into two sub-problems: *virtual node mapping* and *virtual link mapping*. The ordering and criteria to execute them do actually impact on the attained resource utilization and, thereby on the resulting network service performance [9]. In this work, the VNE problem is addressed by the two proposed resource orchestration algorithms being experimentally evaluated within the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed [7] using a pool of figures of merit. More specifically, the following metrics inspired by the VNE problems [26] are considered: the *path length* metric and the *stress level*. With the former, the QoS requirements in terms of end-to-end latency are effectively represented and quantified. In general, the larger is the connection path, the higher the experienced delay is. Thus, the first resource orchestration algorithm leads to select cloud DC resources which do minimize the resulting network delay when providing DC inter-connectivity. The *stress level* indicator reflects the DC occupancy/use. The second resource orchestration algorithm relies on this metric fostering in such a way a load balancing strategy for selecting the DCs to eventually host the required VNFs.

2 Related Works

The topic of allocating both cloud and networking resources considering DCs distributed over transport network infrastructures is getting notable attention [10]. More specifically, in this section, we present a number of VNE approaches and solutions that have been explored recently in the literature aiming at optimally mapping the virtual networks over a substrate infrastructure and guarantee end-to-end network services' requirements [26]. In a nutshell, such mechanisms address the optimal accommodation of virtual network demands from different perspectives. In the literature, there have been a lot of algorithms proposed to solve different VNE problems with different objectives. More specifically, [11] and [13] tackled the assurance of end-to-end QoS by addressing the concept of resource overbooking and exploiting the substrate topology information to increase the resilience of the mapped application, respectively. [14] addressed the survivability of the VNE by considering its economical targets while the energy-efficiency objective was considered in [18][21][19]. Multi-domain virtual network embedding, where geographically distributed resources may need to be abstracted and handled in a multi-domain orchestration fashion is another objective which has several aspects [20] among which we cite scalability and cost reduction issues recently investigated in [15]. Finally, in [17], reliability requirements of end-users have been incorporated

into the VN embedding process with the aim to improve the QoE of the end users especially for delay sensitive applications.

On the other hand, flexi-grid optical networks allow for increasing the flexibility of VNFs deployments while enabling efficient bulk data transfers across DCs. In the optical network scenarios, several works addressed the allocations of VNFs along with optical network paths. In [23], the problem of interconnecting multiple DCs by virtual networks on top of an optical network has been investigated. In [16], authors addressed the problem of optimal VNF placements to chain VNFs in packet/optical DCs while minimizing the expensive optical/electrical/optical (O/E/O) conversions. Additionally, in [22], a combined orchestration process for both cloud and network resources to interconnect multiple DCs over a packet and optical transport infrastructure has been proposed.

The investigated research works address VNF allocations in different scenarios involving optical network interconnections. However, as far as our knowledge, all these approaches focus on optimizing the resource consumption and do not consider the impact of the network delay which is becoming an important requirement when deploying network services across distributed DCs [24]. Last but not least, those proposed solutions have been mostly tested through simulations or within virtualized environments [25] and barely evaluated over experimental testbeds, thus overlooking on the actual feasibility and efficiency of the algorithms in real network deployment scenarios.

3 Resource orchestration set-up in a MLN Infrastructure

The considered cloud/network resource orchestrator system governing the set of distributed DCs interconnected by a MLN is depicted in Fig. 1. This provides the set-up deployment over the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed and is used for conducting the experimental evaluation [5]. The connectivity between a pair of DCs, as said before, is done interconnecting respective packet Gws through a flexi-grid optical network. In the considered MLN scenario, *grooming* decisions are exploited to leverage the best of both packet and optical switching technologies: *i*) statistical multiplexing (i.e., multiple packet traffic flows are transported over the same optical connection), and *ii*) huge transport capacity provided by the optical transmission. The MLN is programmed by a T-SDN controller based on a PCE Central Controller (PCECC) [7]. Upon an incoming network service requiring a packet connection between a pair of DCs hosting two VNFs, the T-SDN Controller triggers a constrained shortest path computation (CSPF) algorithm. The algorithm considers both the technological constraints imposed by the underlying MLN infrastructure as well as the required service and performance objectives. To this end, the algorithm uses as inputs: *i*) the updated state of the network resources (i.e., packet ports utilization, optical spectrum availability, SBVT usage, etc.), *ii*) the network service requirements such as the demanded bandwidth and the maximum tolerated latency. It is worth outlining that established flex-grid

Fig. 1: Resource Orchestration on top of a MLN set-up

optical connections deployed between a pair of packet nodes (Gws) are derived on the so-called virtual packet link (VL). Such VLs inherit attributes (e.g., available bandwidth, accumulated delay, etc.) from their underlying (optical) connections [7], and its spare available bandwidth may be considered by subsequent CSPF computations to accommodate future packet connections demands exploiting the targeted grooming opportunities.

The functions (i.e., network resource computation and MLN programmability) made by the T-SDN controller are coordinated by the cloud/network orchestrator (i.e., the *Allocator*). The *Allocator* acts as the frontend for processing incoming VNFFG requests. This entails several operations: *i*) checking DCs' resource availability, *ii*) deciding selection of both cloud and network resources based on their load and availability, and *iii*) allocating the selected resources (assisted by the T-SDN controller as for network links). In other words, the *Allocator* performs not only cloud/DC selection but also inter-DC path computations based on the retrieved abstracted network information gathered from the T-SDN controller. For the latter, both the *Allocator* and the T-SDN controller communicate among themselves using two APIs: 1) standard Path Computation Element Protocol (PCEP) [30] for requesting path computation and/or instantiating feasible paths derived from the abstracted topology; 2) a proprietary TCP API for retrieving the abstract network information. Thereby, the *Allocator* uses two repositories: *Cloud database* storing the DC cloud resource status, and the *Traffic Engineering Database (TED)* storing the abstracted network topology (i.e., VLs between connected DCs)¹. Recall that VLs are dynamically deployed through the establishment of low-data rate packet connections over coarse flexi-grid optical bandwidth connections. Using the repositories' information, the *Allocator* executes a particular on-line

¹ . The MANO functions and the NFVO are not explicitly shown in the set-up, since their functions that are relevant in this work, i.e., VNFFG request processing and WIM function, are realized by the *Allocator*, that is particularly focused on the dynamic network resource selection and allocation process. Similarly, the DC infrastructure and the VIM functions have not been actually deployed yet emulated.

VNFFG dynamic request generation	
Description	<i>srcDC</i> and number of VMs to allocate with IT (CPU, RAM, and Storage) and Network (Bw and Latency) demand
Num reqs	1000; Poisson (mean interarrival time: 25s); Exponential duration (Holding Time, HT) varied from 200s, 250s, 300s, and 350s
Num VMs per DC in a req	Uniformly distributed [1,5]
Resources per VM	Uniformly distributed: CPU [1,4]cores; RAM [1,6] GB; Storage [4,10,20,40]GB
Network Resources per $Packet_LSP_i$	Bandwidth: uniformly distributed: 10, 40, and 100 Gb/s; Latency: uniformly distributed [6,12]ms

Table 1: VNFFG req generation details

orchestration algorithm to select the (cloud and network) resources fulfilling the VNFFG requirements while meeting specified goals such as minimize the latency and balancing the DC resources load. A detailed description of the two proposed orchestration algorithms is provided in the following section.

4 Algorithms for On-line Cloud and Network Resource Orchestration

Each VNFFG request is assumed to be composed of interconnected VNFs deployed at two remote DCs. VNFs are instantiated over a set of virtual machines (VMs) providing the capacities specified in the network service request. Thus, for every VNFFG request (*req*), cloud resources are allocated into two DCs referred to as (i.e., *srcDC* and *dstDC*). A *req* (Table 1) specifies the number of VMs along with their computing requirements in terms of CPU, RAM and Storage per DC (i.e., *srcDC* and *dstDC*) along with the inter-DC networking requirements: bandwidth (Bytes/s) and maximum tolerated latency (ms). The features of the devised resource orchestration algorithms are thoroughly detailed in the following:

- *Minimum Distance* (MD): given the *srcDC* in the *req*, the MD orchestration algorithm chooses the *dstDC* out of a candidate set of DCs resulting the closest with respect to the distance (km) provided that: *i*) it has sufficient available cloud resources to serve the *req* and, *ii*) the inter-DC bandwidth requirement is ensured. This allows MD minimizing the resulting network delay between both *srcDC* and *dstDC* connectivity leading to better deal with the *req*'s latency upper limit.
- *Less Loaded DC* (LLDC): given the *srcDC* in the *req*, LLDC algorithm chooses the *dstDC* out of a candidate set of DCs having the larger amount of available cloud resources (i.e., less loaded DC) provided that: *i*) it has sufficient available cloud resources to serve the *req*; *ii*) the inter-DC bandwidth requirement is fulfilled, and *iii*) the maximum required tolerated latency is not exceeded.

Fig. 2 shows the control workflows (i.e., interactions between the *Allocator* and the T-SDN Controller) required for MD and LLDC algorithms when serving a VNFFG request. For the sake of completeness, in [6], the authors presented detailed pseudocode descriptions of former algorithms variations similar to both MD and LLDC. Thus, MD and LLDC specific pseudocode definitions can be easily inferred from those tackled in [6].

Regardless of the used algorithm, upon a new *req*, the *Allocator* verifies whether the *srcDC* has enough available computing resources. Additionally, it seeks for a subset of candidate *dstDCs* ensuring the cloud resource demands using either MD or LLDC. If either conditions fails, the *req* is refused.

Focusing on the MD approach, in Fig. 2(a), the *Allocator* sends to the T-SDN controller a PCEP Path Computation Request (PCReq) message to compute a path from the *srcDC*'s Gw to all the possible *dstDCs*' Gws. The PCReq message carries both the Gws endpoints and the requested bandwidth (*Bw*). For each PCReq message, the T-SDN Controller triggers a K-CSPF algorithm (described in [5]) to satisfy both *Bw* and latency constraints. The K-CSPF algorithm aims at finding a feasible MLN path attaining the most efficient use of the network resources (i.e., packet ports, optical spectrum, S-BVT devices, etc.). If a path is found, the T-SDN Controller sends a PCEP Path Computation Reply (PCRep) message to the *Allocator* with the entire path (i.e., nodes, links, frequency slot, modulation format, SBVT's subtransponders) along with a metric value reflecting the actual distance (in km) between the Gw's endpoints. This metric allows the *Allocator* selecting the *dstDC* with the lowest distance (in km). Afterwards, the *Allocator* coordinates the allocation of the selected *dstDC* cloud and network resources over the pre-computed inter-DC path.

In the LLDC approach, in Fig. 2(b), for each candidate *dstDC*, the *Allocator* computes the percentage of the available cloud resources as a ratio between the amount of unused cloud resources over the sum of the whole deployed resources. Next, the *Allocator* selects the DC having the highest ratio, i.e., less loaded DC. Once the *dstDC* is chosen, the *Allocator* retrieves via the T-SDN controller the abstracted network view. Using the set of gathered VLs, the *Allocator* triggers a shortest path computation to connect both *srcDC* and *dstDC* Gws. The targeted objective is to reuse as much as possible the spare available bandwidth of the existing VLs (i.e., grooming strategies). If this succeeds, the *Allocator* sends a PCEP PCInitiate message to the T-SDN controller with the computed route formed by the set of VLs carried into Explicit Route Object (ERO) to perform the network programmability. Otherwise, the *Allocator* cannot find a feasible route (through the set of VLs for connecting both the *srcDC* and *dstDC* Gws), and delegates to T-SDN controller the path computation over the MLN to provide the targeted DC connectivity.

In both resource orchestration strategies, if the DC connectivity succeeds, a PCEP Path Computation Report (PCRpt) message is sent back to the *Allocator*. Conversely, a Path Computation Error (PCErr) is sent to the *Allocator* informing that no connectivity between the selected *srcDC* and *dstDC* Gws is found, and thus the network service request is blocked.

Fig. 2: Cloud/Network Orchestrator - T-SDN controller Workflows

5 Experimental Results

The performance evaluation of the proposed resource orchestration algorithms is conducted within the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed rolling out the cloud/network orchestrator and the MLN infrastructure shown in Fig. 1.

The cloud infrastructure is made up of 5 (emulated) DCs of different size (i.e., supporting different amount of cloud resources) which are connected to their corresponding 5 Gw nodes (i.e., MPLS switches). As indicated in Table 2, we consider 2 small DCs equipped with 40 CPU Cores, 160GB of RAM and 7TB of Storage attached to both Gw2 and Gw3; 2 medium DCs having 80 CPU cores, 320GB of RAM and 10TB of Storage connected to Gw4 and Gw5;

1 large DC with 500 CPU cores, 2400GB of RAM and 135TB of Storage bound to Gw1.

Cloud Infrastructure details (5 emulated DCs)	
2 SMALL	CPU: 40 Cores; RAM: 160GB; Storage: 7TB
2 MEDIUM	CPU: 80 Cores; RAM: 320GB; Storage: 10TB
1 LARGE	CPU: 500 Cores; RAM: 2400GB; Storage: 135TB

Table 2: Information about emulated Data Centers

Each Gw node has a single packet port (operating at 400Gb/s) connected to the optical flexi-grid network via an S-BVT with 10 subtransponders. Each subtransponder can use 3 different modulation formats (MFs), i.e., DP-16QAM, DP-8QAM and DP-QPSK, enabling 3 different bit rates, namely, 200, 150 and 100 Gb/s, for maximum distances, i.e., 650, 1000 and 3000 km, respectively. Optical links support 128 Nominal Central Frequencies with channel spaced of 6.25GHz. Optical fiber distances in Fig. 1 are necessary for determining usable MFs when executing the K-CSPF computation as well as the accumulated path delay for checking the *req* latency restriction. Specific details of the *req* generation including the amount of demanded cloud resources and bandwidth and latency needs are described in Table 1. Each experimental data point is realized with 1000 VNFFG requests following a Poisson process whose mean inter-arrival time is set to 25s. Requests duration is modelled exponentially whose mean (holding time, HT) is varied among 200, 250, 300, and 350 s. This provides different offered traffic loads (expressed in Er): 8, 10, 12, and 14. The requirements of the VNFFG requests are generated as follows: the number of VMs per DC is uniformly distributed between [1,5]; the IT resources (i.e., CPU, RAM and disk) are randomly chosen in the ranges of [1,4] cores, [1,6] GB and [4,10,20,40] GB, respectively; the demanded bandwidth is randomly selected among [10,40,100] Gb/s [12]; and the latency (l) is in the range of [6,12] ms.

Fig. 3 shows the percentage of the accepted *reqs* versus the offered traffic load in Erlangs (Er) when applying either MD or LLDC. Higher rate of accepted *reqs* is attained by LLDC. This means that LLDC objective fostering to prioritize selected *dstDC* being less loaded leads to attain a more efficient use of all DC resources. This in turn does increase the chances to serve future network services. To consolidate this statement, we thoroughly studied the reason why a *req* is blocked. In fig. 4, the two main causes of requests rejection are depicted, namely, the lack of DC's cloud resources and the lack of network resources entailing the unavailability to satisfy the VNFFG's latency and/or bandwidth requirements. That is, for those VNFFG requests not served, it is depicted the number of rejected requests per traffic load related to one of the aforementioned blocking reasons.

Fig. 4(a) shows that most of the blocked requests are due to the cloud resource unavailability in the MD case. This is because the selection of the

Fig. 3: Percentage of accepted requests vs. Traffic Load (Er)

dstDC is exclusively done by minimizing the distance with the *dstDC*. That is, no strategy fostering the efficient compute resource utilization among all DCs is applied. Consequently, this strategy is susceptible to exhaust resources at specific DCs. On the other hand, Fig. 4(b) shows that at lowest traffic load, the rejection caused by the network unavailability is similar for both MD and LLDC. At a traffic load of 12 Er, the LLDC experiences more blocked requests caused by the network unavailability. The rationale behind this is the opposite with respect to the previous case, wherein as traffic load grows the LLDC finds more problems to satisfy the network requirements especially the latency requirement.

(a) Rejection due to Cloud unavailability (b) Rejection due to the Network availability

Fig. 4: Request rejection analysis

Another interesting figure of merit regards the number of induced VLs to potentially accommodate incoming *reqs*. Recall that an induced VL is a (virtual) packet switching link interconnecting a pair of packet node endpoints (i.e., Gws) which is derived over a given established physical flexi-grid optical flow. Fig. 5(a) shows the total number of created VLs when adopting each

resource orchestration algorithm for different traffic load. At low traffic load, MD solution does create a lower number of VLs compared to the LLDC approach. Starting from traffic load equals to 12 Er, we can notice that LLDC creates less VLs than MD approach.

The relevance of this figure of merit is that it inherently reflects how each approach performs on the objective of attaining efficient use of the network resources. In other words, how well the grooming strategy (i.e., multiplexing multiple packet flows) MD and LLDC perform. Indeed, creating less VLs means allocating less optical resources. This entails saving packet ports (i.e., S-BVTs), which allows increasing the likelihood of successfully accommodating future *reqs*. Increasing the traffic load, as expected, more networking resources are occupied, and less VNFFG requests are served. This behaviour is as well reflected on a decreased number of derived VLs.

To put in relation the number of created VLs with the ratio of accepted requests and to show how well an orchestration strategy performs on reusing spare available bandwidth on existing VLs, we derive the curve plotted in Fig. 5(b). Observe that regardless of the traffic load, a small difference between the two strategies appears. In fact, at 8 and 10 Er, both approaches perform similarly in the creation of VLs. The resource allocation enhancement for the MD approach is shown starting from 12 Er, enabling the allocation of more VNFFG requests over the VL already created.

Fig. 5: Virtual Links analysis

Fig. 6 plots the delays experienced by both algorithms. In particular, in Fig. 6(a) the propagation delay from *srcDC* and *dstDC* using the two resource orchestration approaches is depicted. As expected, MD lowers the obtained delay since it performs cloud and network resource computation minimizing the inter-DC path distance. Consequently, MD tends to accomplish the lowest propagation delay. Conversely, LLDC approach attains an accumulated propagation delay almost doubling the one achieved by the MD algorithm. The same behavior is experienced regarding the end-to-end latency, that is represented in Fig. 6(b). As said, LLDC targets a better optimization of the DC

resources whilst the distance between DCs is not minimized. Observe that as the traffic load increases, LLDC propagation delay is smoothly lowered. Indeed, resources are more used which makes more troublesome to deal with the network constraints.

Aligned to the above, it becomes more complicated to satisfy the latency requirement for the incoming requests as shown in Fig. 4(b). Therefore, in LLDC, at high traffic load, successfully established services tend to be deployed over shortest inter-DC paths, which results on shortest propagation delay.

(a) Propagation Delay vs. Traffic Load (Er) (b) End-to-End Latency vs. Traffic Load (Er)

Fig. 6: Experienced delays analysis

Fig. 7 plots the obtained Bandwidth Blocking Ratio (BBR). BBR provides the ratio between the amount of bandwidth being blocked and the total bandwidth requested by all the *reqs*. This metric becomes relevant to show how the K-CSPF algorithm performs when computing paths over the MLN infrastructure targeting grooming opportunities. That is, favouring grooming provides a better use of the network resources, which in turn does lower the BBR. That said, from the results, one may realize that the resource orches-

Fig. 7: Bandwidth Blocking Ratio vs. Traffic Load (Er).

tration algorithm applied in the *Allocator* when selecting *dstDC* has notable impact on the obtained BBR. Observe that as traffic load grows, MD performs better (i.e., lower BBR) when compared to LLDC. The reason behind that is as traffic load grows, network resources are more occupied. This complicates the K-CSPF to find feasible MLN paths (when needed) satisfying the set of imposed technological constraints such as spectrum continuity and contiguity. Adopting a resource orchestration strategy which minimizes the distance between *srcDC* and *dstDC* tends to require less network resources when accommodating a *req*. Thereby, MD selection facilitates the K-CSPF algorithm to deal with those mentioned technological constraints.

Fig. 8: Average usage of Subtransponders

Since different DC sizes are considered, focusing on how physical networking resources are occupied on each DC provides interesting insights to realize about the obtained performance. To this end, the average use of SBVT's subtransponders attached to the DC's Gws is taken. The idea is to correlate the usage of SBVT's subtransponders with the selection of specific DC type. Fig. 8 depicts the average SBVT's subtransponders usage for DC size for each orchestration strategy. Adopting the MD approach (i.e., minimizing inter-DC distance), in Fig. 8(a), we observe that the SBVT's subtransponder at both small and medium size DCs are more occupied. In the considered MLN topology, minimum inter-DC distances are attained between pairs of small and medium DCs. In Fig. 8(b), we can notice that for the LLDC approach starting from traffic load equals to 10 Er, when the network is more loaded, we obtain a highest utilization of the SBVT at the large DC. This is reasonable since large DCs make it more likely to be selected as the *dstDC*.

Regarding the utilization/allocation of physical resources, from the collected data, we noticed that the utilization of the physical resources follow the same trend for each parameter (i.e., CPU, RAM and Storage). For this reason, we have decided to represent only the plots related to the CPU consumption/allocation for each DCs' category (i.e., small, medium, and large).

In Fig. 9, the amount of CPU being allocated for each DC size is shown for the two approaches. MD allocates more VNFs at both small and medium DCs. In Fig. 9(a), the MD approach occupies almost the 60% of the CPU available in the small DCs when the load is equal to 14 Er, whereas the LLDC approach reaches the 50%. This behaviour is also seen for medium DC (Fig. 9(b)). However, this trend is reversed for large DC (Fig. 9(c)) where the MD and LLDC occupy 10% and 20% of the CPU, respectively. In fact, LLDC prioritizes allocating cloud resources in DC having more available resources, which uses to be the larger DCs.

(a) CPU consumption in small DCs in (b) CPU consumption in medium DCs in (c) CPU consumption in large DCs

Fig. 9: CPU consumption in different DC sizes

Finally, Fig. 10 shows the average set-up time, i.e., the overall time required to: *i)* select the *dstDC*, *ii)* compute the inter-DC connectivity, and *iii)* allocate the network resources of such an inter-DC connectivity (either reusing VNs or allocating new MLN resources). As expected from the discussed workflows, MD approach requires longer time to set up the network services mainly due to the amount of control interactions between both the *Allocator* and the T-SDN Controller to derive the shortest path distance for each candidate *dstDC*.

6 Conclusions

In this work, we compared two on-line cloud and network resource orchestration algorithms (MD and LLDC) to dynamically accommodate network services (expressed as VNFFGs) within distributed remote DCs inter-connected through a MLN infrastructure. The performance evaluation of both algorithms has been carried out experimentally within the CTTC ADRENALINE testbed using different figures of merit: the acceptance ratio, the BBR and the consumed CPU resource per DC size for multiple traffic loads. The MD algorithm aims at minimizing the inter-DC connectivity distance between the selected DCs to lower the resulting end-to-end latency. On the other hand, LLDC is devised to attain a better use of the compute resources throughout all the DCs. From the results, we can state that LLDC algorithm does improve the

Fig. 10: Setup time vs. Traffic Load (Er)

network service request acceptance thanks to the beneficial effect of balancing the compute resource load at the expenses of increasing the end-to-end latency.

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